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PERCEIVE

Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences

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D5.2 PERCEIVE Platform

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the final technical documentation and design for the PERCEIVE Platform, a digital ecosystem designed for the preservation and study of coloured cultural heritage collections. At its core, the platform utilizes a Backend-for-Frontend (BFF) pattern to aggregate internal services into optimized endpoints for user interfaces while abstracting the underlying complexity of the service topology.

The deliverable details several advanced heritage tools that bridge the gap between scientific research and practical conservation. These include StyleShade3D for 3D model stylization, the Deep Degreening tool for restoring damaged autochromes, doLCE 2.0 for the reconstruction of early lenticular Kodacolor film, the Light Damage Estimation tool (LDE) that helps researchers estimate light damage to pigments of artworks, the HSLU Migration Tool helps to preserve legacy Augmented Reality artworks by migrating them into contemporary Unity environments.

Validation of the platform's performance confirms it is ready for production environments. The operational integrity is guaranteed by real-time observability and comprehensive logging achieved through the integration of Open Telemetry, Prometheus, and Grafana. Ultimately, these technical foundations create a sustainable and FAIR-compliant framework dedicated to the digital preservation and study of coloured cultural heritage.

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V2.0	2026/01/13	Release working draft	FORTH/NTNU/CNR

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PERCEIVE Platform

As detailed in the first version of this deliverable (D5.2 v1), the PERCEIVE Platform underwent a rigorous selection process involving comprehensive feasibility analyses and risk assessments. The platform consists of several interconnected modules: The Perceive API and Portal, the Tools and the Services. In this final version of the D5.2 deliverable we present the implementation and verification results for these modules focusing mainly on D5.2.2 (API), D5.2.3 (Tools) and D5.2.4 (Services).

D5.2.1: Runtime Environment

The strategic framework for the PERCEIVE runtime environment, ranging from initial requirement finalization to the final risk-assessed trade-off study, was fully documented in the previous deliverable (Section D5.2.1 of D5.2 v1). The decision-making process was designed to ensure that the chosen technology aligned with the project's long-term vision of providing a secure, high-performance, and scalable digital heritage platform. While Python FastAPI was noted as a strong contender in the SWOT analysis, **ASP.NET Core** was deemed superior due to its better overall performance and lower risk profile for the specific needs of the PERCEIVE API.

D5.2.2 API design

.1 Introduction

In this section we present the comprehensive design of the PERCEIVE API, a modern microservices-based system built on .NET 8 that serves as the central communication infrastructure for the PERCEIVE platform. The API design addresses critical requirements for cultural heritage data management, including secure authentication, efficient file handling, asynchronous processing workflows, and real-time monitoring capabilities.

By adopting a decoupled microservices architecture orchestrated through the Backend-for-Frontend (BFF) pattern, the API ensures that frontend clients remain abstracted from the complexity of internal service topology while benefiting from optimised payload aggregation and unified authentication enforcement. This architectural approach enables independent service scaling, technology stack flexibility, and simplified maintenance cycles.

The design prioritises three fundamental pillars: **security** through comprehensive authentication and authorisation layers, **performance** via asynchronous processing and efficient communication protocols, and **observability** through extensive instrumentation and monitoring infrastructure. These design principles ensure the API can reliably support the demanding requirements of cultural heritage digitisation, preservation, and analysis workflows.

Key Achievements:

- **Microservices Architecture:** Implemented a scalable, modular architecture using .NET Aspire orchestration with eight core services communicating via REST, gRPC, and message queues
- **High Performance:** Validated system performance achieving 50+ transactions per second with <1sec response times
- **Comprehensive Security:** OAuth2/OpenID Connect authentication, role-based access control, rate limiting, and end-to-end encryption for data protection
- **Production-Ready Observability:** Full instrumentation with OpenTelemetry, Prometheus metrics collection, and Grafana dashboards for system health monitoring

- **Standards Compliance:** RESTful resource design, OpenAPI/Swagger documentation, standardised error handling (RFC 7807), and FAIR principles integration

Document Structure: D5.2.2 is organised into sections covering the complete API design lifecycle. Section 2 details the architectural foundations including the Backend-for-Frontend pattern, worker communication protocols, and inter-service communication strategies. Section 3 addresses the multi-layered security architecture encompassing authentication, authorisation, and data protection mechanisms. Sections 4-6 define the data exchange models, key API resources, and real-time communication capabilities. Sections 7-8 examine observability infrastructure and performance characteristics, while Section 9 provides validation results of key performance indicators through integration and load testing. The document concludes with documentation strategies (Section 10), a short description of the DCM used (Section 11), a comprehensive requirements verification matrix (Section 12), and overall readiness assessment (Section 13).

.2 API Architecture

The PERCEIVE API architecture is founded on microservices principles, where functional domains are decomposed into independently deployable services that communicate through well-defined protocols. This approach facilitates horizontal scalability, fault isolation, and technology heterogeneity while maintaining system cohesion through standardised communication patterns.

Understanding this architectural foundation is essential for grasping how the system achieves its non-functional requirements for performance, scalability, and maintainability while supporting the complex workflows required for cultural heritage data processing.

.2.1 High-Level Overview

The system architecture flows from the Client applications through the BFF, which routes requests to the appropriate core microservices (see Figure below). These services interact with the infrastructure layer (PostgreSQL, RabbitMQ) and external systems (InvenioRDM).

High-Level API Architecture - This diagram illustrates system topology showing client request flow through the Backend-for-Frontend (BFF) gateway to core microservices (Identity, Authorisation, Data, Metadata, Orchestrator), their interactions with infrastructure components (RabbitMQ message broker) and the processing of a request on the worker (wrapping the PERCEIVE tools)

REST API: The API adopts REST principles for resource manipulation, ensuring predictable and standard interactions with resources such as Users, Orders, and Digital Assets. The API is built using **FastEndpoints**, a performance-focused alternative to minimal APIs, which allows for strongly-typed endpoint definitions and better code organisation.

WORKERS: External Workers communicate with the platform via a message-based protocol using **RabbitMQ**. This asynchronous communication model allows workers to process resource-intensive orders (e.g., AI analysis, 3D reconstruction) without blocking the main API threads.

Inter-Service Communication:

- **gRPC & HTTP/2:** High-performance, low-latency communication is used between internal microservices (e.g., Identity, Email, Data) for synchronous operations.
- **RabbitMQ:** Used for asynchronous event-driven communication (e.g., “Order Created” events).

Routing and Versioning

- **Versioning:** The API supports versioning to ensure backward compatibility (**PERC-API-FR-007**).
- **Routing:** All external traffic is routed through the BFF, which acts as a reverse proxy.

PERCEIVE SYSTEM FLOW

Gateway Integration: The BFF integrates with **YARP (Yet Another Reverse Proxy)** to handle request forwarding and load balancing (**PERC-API-FR-011**). This allows the BFF to transparently proxy requests to downstream microservices while handling cross-cutting concerns like authentication and rate limiting.

Response Structure: All API responses follow a standard JSON output format (**PERC-API-FR-013**), ensuring consistency across all endpoints.

.3 Security Architecture

A multi-layered security architecture is implemented to protect the PERCEIVE platform against unauthorised access, data breaches, and service abuse. Security in a microservices environment presents unique challenges compared to monolithic architectures, requiring defence-in-depth strategies that address authentication, authorisation, transport security, data protection, and attack surface mitigation across distributed service boundaries.

The security architecture implements four primary protection layers: (1) **Authentication** through the Identity Service providing user credential verification, session management, and token-based access using industry-standard ASP.NET Core Identity, (2) **Authorisation** via the OAuth2/OpenID Connect Authorisation Service enforcing fine-grained access policies through role-based (RBAC) and attribute-based (ABAC) control mechanisms, (3) **Protection** mechanisms including rate limiting at the BFF gateway level to defend against denial-of-service attacks and ensure fair resource allocation, and (4) **Data Security** measures encompassing encryption at rest (delegated to the Nextcloud storage with AES-256 encryption) and in transit (TLS 1.2+), along with GDPR compliance procedures including the “Right to be Forgotten” and data portability implemented via API endpoints (Delete, export).

.4 Data Exchange Model

In a distributed microservices architecture, consistent data exchange patterns are critical for system reliability, client predictability, and long-term maintainability. The data exchange model ensures consistency and reliability in how information is shared between clients and services.

- **Standardisation:** Uniform response envelopes are used for internal logic, wrapping data and status codes (**PERC-API-FR-001**).
- **External Service Abstraction:** The API abstracts external providers like InvenioRDM and Nextcloud, exposing internal data models to clients so they remain agnostic of the backend implementation.
- **Error Handling:** Standardised error schemas (RFC 7807) are used (**PERC-API-FR-009**). Upstream failures (e.g., Nextcloud unavailable) are mapped to appropriate standard HTTP codes.
 - *Validation:* Error Response Accuracy (**PERC-API-KPI-1201**) has been verified.
- **Data Retrieval:** Pagination strategies are implemented for endpoints returning large datasets (**PERC-API-FR-003**).
- **File Handling:** Specific protocols are in place for secure file uploads and downloads, managed by the Data Service (**PERC-API-FR-004**).

.5 Key Resources & Endpoints

The API surface is organised around three core resource domains:

1. **Users** (/users) managing user profiles, account settings, and identity information with endpoints supporting registration, authentication, profile updates, and account management operations,
2. **Orders** (/orders) orchestrating processing workflows for cultural heritage analysis tools including order submission, status polling, progress tracking, and result retrieval for asynchronous operations executed by external worker services, and
3. **Resources** (/resources) providing access to digital assets such as high-resolution images, 3D models, and associated metadata with support for upload, download, versioning, and permission management

Note: Comprehensive endpoint definitions are maintained in the OpenAPI/Swagger specifications. For more information on the endpoints please refer to D5.2.4 or the perceive [online documentation](#).

.6 Real-Time Communication

A robust mechanism for providing clients with timely updates about long-running operations is a critical requirement for cultural heritage processing workflows that may execute for minutes or hours. Real-time communication encompasses both the current implementation based on polling patterns and the architectural provisions for future push-based notification systems.

The communication strategy addresses three aspects: (1) **Current State** implementing asynchronous operation patterns where clients submit orders and receive immediate acknowledgment with tracking identifiers, then periodically poll dedicated status endpoints to retrieve progress updates and completion notifications, optimising polling intervals to balance responsiveness against server load, (2) **Future Capability** demonstrating architectural readiness for WebSocket and SignalR integration (**PERC-API-FR-005**), enabling server-initiated push notifications that reduce client complexity and network overhead while providing instantaneous status updates, and (3) **Status Tracking** detailing the end-to-end workflow from worker progress reporting through message queue propagation to Orchestrator state updates and client-facing status endpoints (**PERC-API-FR-006**), including support for granular progress percentages, stage transitions, and error condition communication.

This approach balances immediate production needs with forward compatibility, ensuring the system can evolve to more efficient communication patterns without requiring fundamental architectural changes.

Observability and Monitoring Stack Architecture - This diagram depicts the comprehensive three-tier monitoring infrastructure: (1) PERCEIVE services exposing Prometheus-compatible `/metrics` endpoints, (2) Prometheus time-series database scraping metrics every 15 seconds, and (3) Grafana dashboards visualising system health with Alertmanager providing notification routing to Slack, email, and webhook targets.

.7 Observability & Monitoring

In distributed microservices architectures, observability is not optional but essential for understanding system behaviour, diagnosing failures, and validating performance characteristics against defined KPIs.

The observability stack implements a three-tier architecture (depicted in the Figure above):

1. **Instrumentation** through OpenTelemetry (OTEL) integrated into every service, capturing detailed telemetry including HTTP request metrics (rate, duration, status distribution), runtime metrics (CPU utilisation, memory consumption, garbage collection statistics, thread pool utilisation), database metrics (connection pool health, query latency via Npgsql instrumentation), messaging metrics (RabbitMQ publish/consume rates, message processing duration), and custom business metrics (orders created, workers registered, authentication events),
2. **Collection** via Prometheus configured to scrape standardised /metrics endpoints from all services at fixed (I.e 15seconds) intervals, providing time-series storage with flexible query capabilities through PromQL, and
3. **Visualisation** through Grafana dashboards (Figure below) offering real-time system health views, historical trend analysis, and alerting integration via Alertmanager for threshold-based notifications (**PERC-API-KPI-1001**).

A screenshot of the Perceive Grafana Dashboard showing some of the metrics reporting widgets. Open telemetry enables the transparent collection of business and system metrics and Prometheus/Grafana enable real-time visualisation and querying.

Additionally, health check endpoints (`/health`, `/alive`) enable load balancer health probes and orchestrator-managed service lifecycle (**PERC-API-FR-012**). Finally structured logging via Serilog provides centralised, queryable logs with correlation IDs for distributed request tracing, achieving 100% logging coverage (**PERC-API-KPI-1301**) across all service operations (**PERC-API-NFR-1300**).

.8 Performance & Scalability

Performance and scalability are foundational non-functional requirements that determine whether the system can support production workloads and accommodate future growth without fundamental redesign.

The analysis addresses three performance dimensions:

1. **Throughput & Concurrency** examining the system's capacity to handle high request volumes through load testing validation, demonstrating sustained performance under 50+ concurrent users generating 50+ transactions per second (**PERC-API-NFR-0100**, **PERC-API-NFR-0200**), facilitated by asynchronous programming patterns, efficient database connection pooling, and stateless service design,
2. **Scaling** exploring how the microservices architecture enables horizontal scaling through independent service replication, stateless request handling allowing arbitrary load balancer distribution, message queue decoupling preventing synchronous bottlenecks, and containerised deployment supporting dynamic orchestration via Kubernetes autoscaling (**PERC-API-NFR-0300**),
3. **Latency** measuring response time distributions showing low latency for API operations, significantly exceeding the target threshold of <1000ms (**PERC-API-KPI-0701**), achieved through optimised query patterns, eager loading strategies, caching at multiple layers, and gRPC for inter-service communication.

These performance characteristics validate that the API design supports both current operational requirements and anticipated future growth as the PERCEIVE platform expands its user base and processing capabilities. In the following section we present the validation results.

.9 KPI Validation Results

We present evidence that the PERCEIVE API meets its defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through systematic testing and validation procedures.

The validation methodology employs an automated test suite (part of the perceive API codebase) that can be executed to reproduce the results. The suite comprises three test modules:

1. **Performance Tests** validating throughput, concurrency, scalability, and response time KPIs using authenticated requests against the `POST /api/orders` endpoint to test real business logic (order creation),
2. **Security Tests** validating OAuth2/RBAC implementation, JWT encryption standards, and rate limiting functionality
3. **Monitoring Tests** validating Prometheus/Grafana integration and logging coverage.

For KPIs that require human interaction or human validators we performed **manual validation** and present them separately in section 2.9.3.

All performance tests execute with OAuth2 client credentials authentication, creating actual processing orders to ensure measurements reflect real-world API behaviour rather than simple health check endpoints.

.9.1 Performance & Scalability Validation

KPI ID	Name	Target	Result	Status
PERC-API-KPI-0101	Throughput Efficiency	> 50 TPS	748 TPS	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-0201	Concurrent Request Load	> 50 users	50 concurrent, 100% handled	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-0301	Scalability Flexibility	+50% capacity	Baseline 803 RPS, Stress 532 RPS	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-0701	Response Time	< 1000 ms (P95)	53 ms P95	Pass
PERC-T&S-KPI-0501	Response Time Efficiency	< 200 ms (avg)	24 ms avg	Pass
PERC-T&S-KPI-0502	Performance Under Load	< 300 ms (avg)	245 ms avg	Pass

Note: Rate limiting (HTTP 429) when active is correctly throttling excessive requests. This is expected behaviour demonstrating proper system protection under load.

.9.2 Security & Compliance Validation

KPI ID	Name	Description	Result	Status
PERC-API-KPI-0401	Security Compliance	Verifies the API's compliance with OWASP security standards	OAuth2/OIDC verified, protected endpoints secured	Yes
PERC-API-KPI-1401	Encryption Compliance	Compliance rate with specified encryption standards for stored data	NextCloud storage encryption used for all stored files. Per service databases (I.e Authentication Service) on production deployment will be stored on encrypted file systems.	Yes
PERC-T&S-KPI-0202	Encryption Standard	Verifies system's compliance with encryption standards.	Data at rest encrypted via Nextcloud storage provider (AES-256). TLS 1.2+ for data in transit.	Yes

.9.3 Observability & Quality Validation

KPI ID	Name	Target	Result	Status
PERC-API-KPI-1001	Monitoring Integration	YES	Prometheus/Grafana/Alertmanager active	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-1201	Error Response Accuracy	95%	Verified (401, 404, 429 responses correct)	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-1301	Logging Coverage	>90%	100% coverage via OpenTelemetry	Pass

.9.4 Manual Validation

KPI ID	Name	Description	Result	Status
PERC-API-KPI-0501	Legal Compliance	Ensures the API adheres to legal and regulatory standards	API implementation follows open standards and best practices. Further compliance of the API beyond that depends on the ToS documentation and legal agreements that will be part of the platform's commercialisation process in the future	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-0601	Maintenance Efficiency	Target <8hours per week	Preliminary validation deployment of the system shows that maintenance is <1h per week . This is expected to increase with regular users on production but not significantly.	Pass

PERC-API-KPI-0801	Documentation Quality	Likert scale (>4.5/5)	Extensive effort has been put into creating a comprehensive documentation for the PerceiveAPI. Evaluating the documentation internally by FORTH team members resulted in high degrees of satisfaction (4.5 out of 5 with some comments on clarity which were addressed). Future work is the evaluation by third party developers (external to the PERCEIVE consortium)	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-0901	Data Privacy Compliance	Compliance with GDPR and other data privacy regulations	No sensitive user data is stored in the system. Proper consent management, authentication, encryption and logging are implemented. Definition of privacy policy, Data retention policy and Data processing agreements are currently beyond the scope of PERCEIVE API development, and should be implemented before going into production. Overall the framework for a GDPR compliant system is set.	Pass
PERC-API-KPI-1101	Integration Time	Time required to integrate and deploy new modules or services (<5 days)	Integrating new Tools as part of the worker architecture requires less than one working day (<1day). Measured repeatedly during the integration of the PERCEIVE partners' Tools into the platform.	Pass

.10 Documentation & Maintenance

This section addresses the critical but often undervalued aspects of API longevity: comprehensive documentation enabling developer productivity and maintainability characteristics determining long-term operational costs. Well-documented, maintainable systems reduce onboarding friction, accelerate integration timelines, and minimise the expertise required for system evolution.

The documentation strategy encompasses two primary artifacts:

1. **OpenAPI/Swagger Specifications** providing machine-readable API definitions in OpenAPI 3.0 format, automatically generated from endpoint metadata ensuring documentation-code synchronisation, exposing interactive Swagger UI endpoints for each service during development, supporting client code generation for multiple languages, and enabling contract testing to detect breaking changes (**PERC-API-NFR-0800**), targeting >4.5/5 documentation quality rating (**PERC-API-KPI-0801**), and
2. **Architectural Documentation** including this deliverable (D5.2.2 and D5.2.4), service-specific technical manuals covering authentication flows, deployment procedures, monitoring setup, and

integration guides maintained in markdown format within the repository for version control and collaborative editing. Additionally, a static html manual is generated from the markdown (using the mkdocs tool) and hosted by [FORTH](#) to enable web-based access to the documentation.

The maintenance characteristics stem from architectural decisions favouring modularity and separation of concerns:

1. **Service Independence** allowing individual services to be updated without coordinating changes across the entire system,
2. **Standardised Patterns** reducing cognitive load through consistent authentication, error handling, and logging patterns across services,
3. **Comprehensive Testing** enabling confident refactoring through integration test suites validating behaviour preservation, and
4. **Clear Boundaries** establishing well-defined service contracts that minimise unintended coupling. These properties collectively support the maintenance efficiency target of <8 hours per week (**PERC-API-KPI-0601**) for routine system updates and issue resolution (**PERC-API-NFR-0600**).

.11 Development Collaboration Module (DCM)

During development of the PERCEIVE API (Services, modules etc) a common set of collaboration tools was required through which all involved parties could synchronise and collaborate. As described in D5.1 and detailed in specs (FRs, NFRs, KPIs) in D5.2 the DCM integrates:

1. a code repository and version control system for efficient management of the project's codebase,
2. an issue tracking system to organise and address software development tasks, and
3. a Wiki for comprehensive documentation and internal communication.

It ensures streamlined code development, effective problem-solving, and knowledge sharing, forming the backbone of collaborative efforts within the project team.

To this end, in PERCEIVE we choose early on to rely on the private repositories of github. This cloud service offers industry leading git integration, issue tracking and wiki functionality in a secure and intuitive web interface that is familiar to the majority of software developers. As such it fully conforms with all functional and non-functional requirements of the project (**PERC-DCM-FR-[001-013]**, **PERC-DCM-NFR-[0100-0800]**, section 3.1.4.2) while meeting all specified KPIs (**PERC-DCM-KPI-[0101-0801]**, section 3.1.4.2).

.12 Requirements Verification

The following table summarises how the API Design meets the defined functional and non-functional requirements. For simplicity we present them all in a single table. For the expanded descriptions of FRs, NFRs, the reader may refer to the full tables in section 3 (D5.2.1) of the first version of D5.2.

FR/NFR ID	Name	Status	Implementation / Verification
PERC-API-FR-001	Standardized response format	Implemented	Uniform response envelopes used across all endpoints (Section 4).
PERC-API-FR-002	CORS support	Implemented	Configured in BFF to allow cross-origin requests from Portal.
PERC-API-FR-003	Pagination support	Supported	Architecture supports it and can be implemented in the feature if needed
PERC-API-FR-004	File Uploads	Implemented	Data Service and Metadata service implement endpoints for file uploading to

			Nextcloud and InvenioRDM respectively (service implementation details in D5.2.4)
PERC-API-FR-005	WebSocket communication	Supported	Architecture supports SignalR; currently using polling (Section 6).
PERC-API-FR-006	Progress reporting	Implemented	Async status updates from Workers to Orchestrator (Section 6).
PERC-API-FR-007	Versioning	Implemented	URI-based versioning supported (Section 2).
PERC-API-FR-008	Use Authentication	Implemented	Implemented in the Authentication service (implementation details in D5.2.4)
PERC-API-FR-009	Error handling	Implemented	Standard RFC 7807 error schemas (Section 4).
PERC-API-FR-010	Rate limiting	Implemented	YARP-based rate limiting at BFF level (Section 3).
PERC-API-FR-011	API gateway / BFF integration	Implemented	YARP acting as BFF/Gateway (Section 2).
PERC-API-FR-012	Health check endpoints	Implemented	/health and /alive endpoints exposed (Section 7).
PERC-API-FR-013	JSON format output	Implemented	All APIs return standard JSON (Section 2).
PERC-API-NFR-0100	High throughput	Met	Validated via load testing (Section 9).
PERC-API-NFR-0200	Concurrent request handling	Met	Validated for 50+ concurrent users (Section 9).
PERC-API-NFR-0300	Scalability	Met	Microservices architecture supports horizontal scaling (Section 8).
PERC-API-NFR-0400	Data Security	Met	All API endpoints are exposed with https. Uploaded files are stored in backends (Nextcloud, InvenioRDM) supporting encryption.
PERC-API-NFR-0500	Compliance	Met	API is GDPR compliant, no sensitive user data is stored. RBAC implementation ensures controlled access to sensitive or IP protected data
PERC-API-NFR-0600	Maintenance easy	Met	Modular microservices design (see D5.2.4)
PERC-API-NFR-0700	Performance (Response Time)	Met	p95 latency < 1000ms validated (Section 9).
PERC-API-NFR-0800	Documentation quality	Met	OpenAPI/Swagger specs available, developer manual (Section 10).
PERC-API-NFR-0900	Data Privacy	Met	No personal data are stored. Following GDPR privacy regulations (see PERC-API-KPI-0901)

PERC-API-NFR-1000	Monitoring integration	Met	OpenTelemetry, Prometheus, Grafana stack (Section 7).
PERC-API-NFR-1100	Modular Integration Support	Met	Microservices based implementation based on open standards ensures modular integration of future back-end services and new API endpoints (see PERC-API-KPI-1101).
PERC-API-NFR-1200	Error Handling	Met	Properly implemented error handling in all API endpoints. (Section 4, see also PERC-API-KPI-1201)
PERC-API-NFR-1300	Logging standards	Met	Serilog structured logging (Section 7).
PERC-API-NFR-1400	Data Encryption	Met	NextCloud supports strong data encryption for stored files (see D5.2.4)

.13 Conclusions

D5.2.2 presents a comprehensive examination of the PERCEIVE API design, demonstrating a production-ready system that successfully addresses the complex requirements of cultural heritage data management through modern microservices architecture principles.

Architectural Soundness: The system implements proven design patterns including Backend-for-Frontend for client optimisation, asynchronous messaging for workflow decoupling, and protocol heterogeneity (REST, gRPC) for performance optimisation. The microservices decomposition achieves appropriate service granularity, balancing modularity benefits against operational complexity.

Security Posture: Multi-layered security controls implementing OAuth2/OpenID Connect industry standards, rate limiting for attack mitigation, and end-to-end encryption demonstrate compliance with security requirements (**PERC-API-KPI-0401**) suitable for managing sensitive cultural heritage data. GDPR compliance mechanisms address privacy requirements (**PERC-API-KPI-0901**), with clear roadmaps for enhancing automation of data subject rights processes.

Performance Validation: Testing validates exceptional performance characteristics, achieving throughput targets with latency bellow required target (<1sec). The system demonstrates linear scalability potential through stateless design and message queue decoupling, supporting future growth without architectural rework.

Operational Readiness: Comprehensive observability infrastructure with 100% logging coverage (**PERC-API-KPI-1301**), real-time metrics dashboards, and health monitoring provides the operational visibility necessary for production deployment. Standardised documentation via OpenAPI specifications and extensive integration test coverage support ongoing maintenance with minimal effort (**PERC-API-KPI-0601**).

Production Readiness: All validated KPIs meet or exceed targets, demonstrating system readiness for production. The architecture provides clear evolution paths for planned enhancements (I.e WebSocket communication) without requiring fundamental redesign. The PERCEIVE API successfully establishes the technical foundation necessary to support the platform’s research and preservation objectives.

The PERCEIVE API is architecturally sound, secure, and performant. It meets the defined Functional and Non-Functional requirements and has passed initial validation for key performance indicators.

D5.2.3 Perceive Tools

.1 Introduction

This chapter details the tools developed under the PERCEIVE project, focusing on their design, implementation, and integration. Managed by NTNU, these tools aim to support AI-based colour restoration and create immersive web-based experiences. The tools are divided into two categories: AI tools and traditional tools.

- **Machine Learning based Tools:** This category includes studies on Deep Learning Framework Support, where each framework undergoes feasibility, financial, SWOT, and risk assessments and have been fully documented in the previous deliverable.
- **Image and Signal Processing based Tools:** This category includes Image and Signal Processing tools, evaluated through similar comprehensive analyses and have been fully documented in the previous deliverable.

Document Structure: D5.2.3 is organised into sections covering the PERCEIVE tools. The deliverable covers four main components: **Section 2** StyleShade3D, which applies distinct styles and shading to 3D model segments using learning-based methods; **Section 3** the Deep Degreening Tool, which removes greening defects from damaged images using AI; **Section 4** the Tet2Autochromes tool, a generative AI approach for creating autochrome images from text, including simulation of greening defects; **Section 5** Dolce 2.0, which extends the original doLCE method from the University of Basel with deep learning and user-guided refinement for faithful restoration of historically significant materials; and **Section 6** the MulAX tool to access, discover and examine diagnostic and analytical data available for 2D and 3D multi-layered artefact collections; a Web3D/WebXR tool; **Section 7**. The HSLU Migration Tool; **Section 8**. the Light Damage Estimator (LDE), a web-based app to predict and visualize colour changes for cultural heritage materials, such as paintings, textiles, and paper, caused by light exposure

.2 StyleShade3D

.2.1 General Description and Scope

StyleShade3D is a tool that enhances the process of segment-wise rendering by allowing users to apply distinct styles and shading to different regions of a 3D model utilising learning-based method. It is built on WebGL, a JavaScript API for rendering interactive 2D and 3D graphics in a web browser. The tool utilises a 2D parameterised segmentation map (segmentation atlas) over the 3D surface, which is created through a combination of deep learning-based methods and traditional 3D mesh processing techniques to select the different segments. The workflow (see Figure 1) begins with generating a segmentation atlas, a 2D parameterised uv-map over the 3D surface that represents various segments of a 3D model. This is achieved by rendering multi-view images of the model using camera animations to ensure comprehensive coverage. We use an approach inspired by path planning approaches used in robotic applications to identify minimum set of views necessary to accurately represent the 3D surface. Once the segmentation atlas is generated from the backend service (the tool for this backend service is ongoing work), StyleShade3D leverages this semantic information, deep stylisation models, and shading models to enable region-specific stylisation and shading. This allows artists, designers and curators to easily apply different materials and visual styles to specific areas of the 3D model to showcase potential restoration of the 3D objects like statues.

Overview of the workflow for styling and shading different segments of the 3D model and finally visualising using our StyleShade3D tool.

.2.2 User Requirements and Technical Approach

Creating mockups of pigments based on scientific analysis is a common practice in conservation science. Additionally, photographic documentation and other artworks provide representations of the colours found in various 3D cultural heritage Items. As a result, multiple colour simulations of the original 3D objects can be generated to explore potential hypotheses about their reconstructed colours. However, the criteria for segmentation can change with new evidence, making it challenging to train an AI model that works effectively across all 3D models. To address these challenges, our workflow enables faster segmentation of regions using AI with user guidance. We focus on the image space, where segmentation algorithms are generally more advanced and accurate compared to 3D. This approach allows us to integrate high-quality scans of 3D objects, such as those obtained from laser scanners, with deep learning techniques like image segmentation, style transfer, material parameter estimation, and inpainting. This combination enhances the accuracy and efficiency of our segmentation process, ultimately contributing to efficient conservation outcomes.

.2.3 Key Features and Functionalities

The backend service provides functionality to create various segments of a statue based on user input. Users can choose different materials for each segment, allowing for simulations that showcase potential colour variations. Additionally, the tool enables users to adjust the colour temperature of the light, enhancing the visualization of the segments. It also presents detailed descriptions of the material properties for each segment, facilitating a better understanding of the choices available.

.2.4 User Scenarios

In this user scenario, a conservation scientist conducts a scientific analysis of a 3D object, such as a statue. Based on this analysis, the scientist segments an image of the statue using our AI service and collaborates with technical experts, uploading the image to a data server. The scientist can also upload style images and material properties obtained from devices like Total Appearance Capture (TAC7). Technical experts then use the segmentation image, guided by scientists, to quickly generate segmentation atlas. The tool allows for the application of different styles and materials to various parts of the statue. The results are shared via a web link, enabling the conservation scientist to review all options and select the most plausible reconstructions.

.2.5 Impact and Added Value

The AI-driven segmentation tool greatly improves how conservation scientists work on restoring objects like statues. It allows them to quickly create a segmentation atlas from uploaded images, saving time and letting them focus on important tasks. By collaborating with technical experts, they can achieve accurate

reconstructions. The tool also offers the flexibility to apply different styles and materials, helping them to understand different potential restorations. With access to detailed information about materials, scientists can make better choices that maintain the original look of the statue. Sharing the results through a web link helps professionals work together and learn from each other, ultimately enhancing the quality of restoration efforts and helping to protect cultural heritage.

.2.6 Sustainability and Future Developments

The use of this AI-driven segmentation tool promotes sustainability in conservation by optimising resource utilisation. By streamlining the restoration process, the tool reduces the need for excessive materials and resources, leading to more environmentally friendly practices. As the tool evolves, future developments aim to further enhance its capabilities. The backend service will be integrated as an additional tool, minimising the reliance on technical experts and making the technology more accessible to conservation scientists. Additionally, the tool will support the export and import of reconstructions, facilitating easier sharing and collaboration across projects.

.3 Deep Degreening Tool

.3.1 General Description and Scope

Autochromes represent one of the pioneering advancements in colour photography and hold a vital place in the history of visual arts. Their unique composition makes them exceptionally fragile and sensitive to light, resulting in irreversible damage when they deteriorate. In our project, PERCEIVE, we developed AI models that can restore digitised autochromes that display greening defects. The de-greening tool uses this AI service to de-green the input defected image (see Figure 2).

.3.2 User Requirements and Technical Approach

User interface of the deep de-greening tool.

The objective is to restore digitised autochrome photographs that exhibit greening defects completely or partially. In case of partial removal curators and designers should be able to address the remaining image issues after the green regions are removed in a shorter timeframe. To achieve this, we generate synthetic greening defects through image processing, as we lack reference or ground-truth images for restoration. Our analysis of genuine defects shows they typically manifest as small, point-like stains or larger leakage-style areas, both featuring multi-ringed green halos with subtle orange borders. We simulate these effects by randomly selecting whether an image receives only spot defects, only large area defects, or a combination of both. This process yields a diverse dataset of images with realistic greening defects, which serve as a foundation for training our restoration networks.

.3.3 Key Features and Functionalities

Our de-greening tool offers several model checkpoints; each trained on different loss functions and slightly varied datasets, allowing users to choose the one that best suits their needs. Users can easily select their preferred model checkpoint and specify the desired scale for the output image (see Figure 2). Once these options are set; they can run the algorithm to generate a de-greened image. This flexibility ensures that users can tailor the restoration process to achieve optimal results based on their specific requirements. The interface is designed to be user-friendly, making it simple for anyone to restore their autochrome photographs effectively.

.3.4 User Scenarios and User Profiles

One scenario involves a museum curator who discovers an old autochrome photograph with greening defects. To restore the image, the curator accesses restoration tool, selects a suitable model checkpoint based on prior successes, and specifies the desired output scale before running the algorithm to de-green the image. After reviewing the results, if satisfied, the curator may perform additional post-processing with image editing tools or send the image to a designer or specialist curator for further refinement. Another scenario features an amateur photographer who encounters a digitised autochrome in their collection that has developed greening defects. They use the same restoration tool to select a model checkpoint and set the output scale before running the algorithm. Upon evaluating the de-greened image, they may enhance it further with their favorite editing software or seek feedback from a professional. In both cases, the tool can display the original image alongside the restored version whenever shared, helping to preserve the integrity of the historical photographs and ensuring sensitivity to their cultural heritage significance. These scenarios highlight the needs of both museum curators, who prioritise preservation and integrity, and hobbyists, who seek user-friendly tools that allow for experimentation while understanding the importance of historical context.

.3.5 Impact and Added Value

The restoration tool helps in the preservation of autochrome photographs, offering both museum curators and amateur photographers a means to effectively address greening defects while maintaining the integrity of these historical artifacts. For hobbyists, the tool provides a user-friendly platform to experiment with image restoration, fostering a deeper appreciation for historical photography. By allowing users to view the original and restored images side by side, the tool promotes awareness of the importance of preserving the authenticity of historical works. Overall, the tool adds substantial value by streamlining the restoration process, making it accessible to a broader audience, and promoting sensitivity to the historical context of autochromes.

.4 Text2Autochromes

.4.1 General Description and Scope

The previous section explains how we can remove greening defects from digitised autochromes by creating synthetic greening defects using image processing techniques. In this section, we utilise generative AI to generate autochrome images from text, including those with greening defects. This innovative method enables amateur users to create autochromes based on textual data while allowing AI experts to generate defects in

autochromes for which no references exist. Our new approach employs generative models to create images that capture the unique qualities of autochromes. This also involves simulating common defects such as greening and cracking to develop machine learning methods for restoring real autochrome images with such defects. By generating synthetic defects, such as images with greening issues, we can create a dataset of defected and non-defected autochrome image pairs. This will allow us to train an AI model that learns to effectively remove these greening defects, potentially restoring the integrity of autochrome images.

Text2Autochrome demo!

User interface of the Text2Autochrome tool.

.4.2 User Requirements and Technical Approach

There is no reference available for the greening defects present in digitised autochrome images, making the synthetic simulation of these defects crucial. Text2Autochromes leverages generative AI to create such defects from textual descriptions, fulfilling the need for data that AI experts require. This tool also allows designers and amateur users to create content in the style of autochrome images. However, it is important that such content is explicitly labeled as AI-generated to address ethical concerns regarding AI generated images. To train a diffusion model to generate distinctive autochrome style, we collected 420 high-resolution scans from glass-plate photographs, each paired with its original caption. These images were resized for GPU memory,

and the prompts were slightly rephrased to enhance the training dataset. We then finetuned the FLUX.1-dev model using Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA). Throughout the training process, we closely monitored sample outputs and computed CLIPScore, a text–image compatibility metric, using varied prompts to detect any signs of overfitting.

.4.3 Key Features and Functionalities

The tool provides utilises the AI backend service for generating autochromes from user prompts. Users can create images in various aspect ratios to suit their specific needs. Additionally, the system allows for the selection of different checkpoints, enabling users to tailor the generation process according to their requirements (see Figure 03). Key parameters such as guidance scale and the number of inference steps can be adjusted to influence the output quality and style. Furthermore, users can utilise a seed value to ensure consistent generation across multiple iterations with the same text prompt, enhancing the coherence and reliability of the generated autochrome images.

.4.4 User Scenarios and User Profiles

This tool is designed to cater to a diverse range of users, each with unique needs and objectives. Amateur photographers are interested in experimenting with autochrome styles to enhance their photography; they can input text prompts describing their desired scenes and receive AI-generated images that mimic the distinctive qualities of autochromes. Graphic designers looking to incorporate vintage style aesthetics into their projects can use the tool to generate autochrome style images, adjusting parameters like aspect ratio and guidance scale to achieve the desired visual effect. Additionally, AI experts can utilise this tool for generating synthetic defects in autochrome images, such as greening or cracking, which are essential for training machine learning models aimed at restoring and enhancing the quality of these historical photographs.

.4.5 Impact and Added Value

The generative AI tool specifically enables the creation of synthetic defects where no ground truth exists for the restored image, addressing the lack of reference for greening and other imperfections in autochrome photography. This capability allows AI experts to generate training data essential for developing machine learning models focused on image restoration, significantly advancing the field of digital preservation.

.5 doLCE 2.0 - Lenticular Kodacolor Reconstruction

.5.1 General Description and Scope

The Lenticular Colour Reconstruction Tool (doLCE 2.0) is a software framework developed within the PERCEIVE project to recover the original colour information embedded in early lenticular films such as Kodacolor. It extends the pioneering doLCE method originally conceived at the University of Basel, integrating recent advances in deep learning and user-guided refinement to achieve more faithful digital restorations of these historically significant materials. The tool enables cultural heritage professionals, researchers, and audiovisual archivists to reconstruct full-colour digital images from monochrome lenticular film scans, thereby preserving rare early colour cinematography and ensuring its accessibility for future generations. doLCE 2.0 forms part of PERCEIVE Scenario 4 (Colour Reconstruction in Historical Film), where it serves both as a research instrument and a practical preservation solution. By combining computational imaging, neural modelling, and heritage expertise, the system bridges the gap between historical technology and contemporary digital conservation practice.

.5.2 User Requirements and Technical Approach

The development of doLCE 2.0 has been guided by the needs of film archives, conservation scientists, and audiovisual restoration specialists seeking robust and accessible means to decode lenticular colour information without dependence on obsolete optical projection equipment. Archival institutions require a reproducible and

transparent digital workflow that transforms high-resolution film scans into perceptually accurate colour reconstructions. Researchers demand methodological rigour and the ability to compare algorithmic outputs with historical documentation and physical evidence. Curators and educators, in turn, benefit from visual reconstructions that communicate the aesthetic qualities of early colour film to contemporary audiences. From a technical perspective, doLCE 2.0 implements a modular, data-drive pipeline that combines traditional signal processing with deep neural network architectures. The tool detects the microscopic lenticular pattern embossed on the film base and translates its spatially encoded silver densities into RGB colour channels. The updated version introduces adaptive finetuning mechanisms based on user-validated training data, substantially improving performance on heterogeneous or degraded source material. Implementation within the PERCEIVE microservice infrastructure ensures interoperability, scalability, and long-term maintainability. Data handling adheres to FAIR principles, supporting integration with film digitisation workflows and institutional repositories.

.5.3 Key Features and Functionalities

doLCE 2.0 provides a suite of analytical and visual modules for the decoding and colour reconstruction of lenticular film material.

User interface of the Lenticular Colour Reconstruction Tool.

Key features include Automated lenticule detection and alignment, using convolutional neural networks finetuned on representative training datasets.

- User-guided finetuning workflow, enabling experts to iteratively improve model accuracy through manual correction or automatic selection of plausible frames.
- Colour reconstruction and calibration, transforming the encoded silver densities into RGB images consistent with known spectral characteristics of Kodacolor and related processes.
- Export functionality, generating downloadable, colour-accurate frames ready for archival, analysis, or visualisation.

Access to the tool is provided through the PERCEIVE web interface for registered users (Figure. 04), with planned future release under an open or community license. Its modular design ensures compatibility with complementary services within the platform, including the PERCEIVE Knowledge Repository and colour analysis tools.

.5.4 Use Scenarios and User Profiles

The tool supports a range of professional and research contexts in film preservation, computational imaging, and historical reconstruction. Typical workflows include:

- Film archivists and conservators, who apply doLCE 2.0 to digitally restore lenticular films such as Kodacolor, ensuring faithful colour recovery without analogue projection.
- Researchers in heritage science and image processing, who use the system to test algorithmic methods for colour decoding and to study historical optical encoding techniques.
- Curators and educators, who employ reconstructed footage to illustrate the evolution of early colour cinema and its technological heritage.
- Public audiences, who experience re-created colour sequences that were previously inaccessible or misidentified as black-and-white materials.

A representative case study within PERCEIVE involved the reconstruction of a 1930 travelogue to the Norwegian fjords by amateur filmmaker Arnold Hennings. This 16 mm Kodacolor segment presented severe decoding challenges due to degraded lenticular patterns. By finetuning the deep-learning model with a dataset of manually corrected and visually validated frames, doLCE 2.0 achieved stable and historically plausible colour reproduction. The iterative workflow—combining expert correction and automatic frame selection—demonstrated significant gains in accuracy, producing a coherent and visually credible restoration of the original colour imagery.

.5.5 Impact and Added Value

doLCE 2.0 represents a major step forward in the digital preservation of early colour film heritage. By transforming high-resolution scans into authentic colour reconstructions, the tool bridges the technological gap between obsolete lenticular systems and modern digital imaging. It contributes to the rediscovery and scholarly understanding of the origins of colour cinema, enriching both film history and conservation practice. For the heritage community, doLCE 2.0 offers several tangible benefits:

- Protect vulnerable acetate film materials by replacing mechanical projection with a fully digital decoding process.
- Generate standardised digital outputs that can be archived, studied, and shared between institutions.
- Promotes interdisciplinary collaboration among computer scientists, conservators, and historians, fostering a shared methodological framework for colour reconstruction.
- Enhance public engagement by making early colour footage visible again, providing a unique window into historical visual culture.

By embedding advanced machine-learning techniques in an accessible and transparent interface, doLCE 2.0 exemplifies how data-driven approaches can be responsibly applied to cultural heritage. It transforms technical research into

.6 MuLaX tool

.6.1 General Description and Scope

"MuLaX" (Multi-Layer eXtensible eXplorer) is a Web3D/WebXR tool built on top of the open-source ATON framework by CNR ISPC. It allows users to access, discover and examine diagnostic and analytical data available for 2D and 3D multi-layered artefact collections namely paintings, textiles, sculptures and frescoes.

The main focus of MuLaX is to enable the interactive discovery of invisible (or lost) information made accessible through diagnostic processes. It offers an increased readability of the artwork while exploring new ways to access and examine multi-dimensional items, directly in a web browser.

.6.2 User Requirements and Technical Approach

The MuLaX tool has been designed to address the needs of two main target groups:

1. The first target group comprises experts, including conservation scientists, academic researchers, and museum professionals. Their core need arises from the fragmented nature of diagnostic practices: each analytical method (e.g. multispectral or hyperspectral imaging, spectroscopy, microscopy, graphical plots) produces outputs that differ in scale, format, and nature. This diversity makes collaboration difficult, as there is no unified environment in which to visualise all results together. Experts therefore need a web-based 3D platform that enables them to align heterogeneous data on the same digital replica of an artefact, switch seamlessly between datasets, and refer to the same point, area, or layer, facilitating effective communication and collaborative interpretation.
2. The second target group is the general public, including museum visitors, students, and schools. Their needs are centered on outreach and communication. For them, it is not enough to see visual reconstructions of cultural heritage artefacts; it is essential to understand the scientific evidence that supports these reconstructions. MuLaX addresses this by enabling the rapid creation of tailored exhibits and interactive demonstrations, where curated diagnostic datasets can be explored directly on 3D artefacts. In this way, non-experts can engage with the data behind reconstructions, gaining awareness of heritage science while experiencing cultural artefacts in an accessible, interactive experience.

.6.3 Key Features and Functionalities

The Web3D/WebXR tool offers several functionalities to final users.

Layer Discovery: a prominent feature of MuLaX tool is the multi-layer discovery. For data collected over the entire object (layer data), MuLaX can load it underneath the natural colour layer - typically visible information. It can then be inspected interactively using either the lens or the split view tool. The Lens Tool allows to interactively and locally discover additional data beneath the colour layer or visible information. As the user moves the tool over the surface of the 3D or 2D object, the required layer is revealed within the lens radius. This allows the user to 'explore' the surface, focusing attention on the discovered area. Alternatively, another exploration mode named split view tool, can be used to interactively reveal the hidden bottom layer in the X, Y, or Z axes.

Point Data Mode: this mode enables users to examine data collected from a specific area or region of the object point by point. This data can be in the form of a graph (e.g. XRF, FORS, Raman spectra) or an image (e.g. a UV micro or macro photograph).

Annotations and Masks: MuLaX supports the creation of POIs (points-of-interest) to enrich the item punctually with associated data. These POIs can be classified with categories or techniques, providing live filtering in MuLaX. Masks on the other hand, allows to define more complex, image-based semantic areas, furthermore offering in perspective selective style transfers or selective material parameters control on both 2D or 3D items. Masks can be fetched from other services/tools, cloud storage or interactively generated by users via semantic painting.

XR Inspection: The tool offers the possibility (via WebXR API) to present and inspect a given item in immersive VR, or mixed/augmented reality modes. This offers a way to inspect full-scale digital replicas through a spatial exploration. The tool also extends base ATON spatial UI components to provide a dedicated

spatial UI toolkit. This toolkit offers spatial components for VR or AR sessions to inspect and discover the item enriched with POIs and masks previously described.

.6.4 Use Scenarios and User Profiles

The MuLaX tool's structure has been designed to address two main use scenarios, spanning both expert and public engagement.

1. **Experts:** for academic researchers, heritage scientists, and museum professionals, MuLaX offers a unified platform to annotate, compare, and visualise diagnostic data directly on 3D models of cultural artefacts. The typical workflow involves performing analyses (e.g., spectroscopy, multispectral imaging, microscopy), uploading the resulting data into MuLaX, and aligning them with the 3D virtual replica of the analyzed object \cite{Ferdani2025-tx}. Researchers can then enrich the dataset with descriptive images and structured metadata. Once the 3D dataset is configured within the platform, users are able to collaboratively explore the multi-layered data across desktop, mobile, or XR interfaces.
2. **Public:** for the general public (or visitors interested in heritage science, including schools and students), the tool becomes a medium for interactive demonstration: curated diagnostic datasets, visual overlays, and descriptive annotations can be presented as guided digital exhibits. The workflow here focuses on the rapid assembly of content, designing a tailored narrative for the target audience, and deploying the demo for access via desktop, mobile, or immersive VR/AR environments. In this way, MuLaX serves not only as an analytical backend but also as a versatile exploratory tool, bridging rigorous scientific investigation with accessible public outreach.

.6.5 Impact and Added Value

MuLaX presents a considerable step forward in enabling an intuitive and easy way of investigating all possible analytical data available for an artwork. Users can switch easily between data types be it complete layers or point/areal data. Experts can quickly and visually compare and understand analytical measurements taken from all available data modalities: a paradigm which allows for a more holistic analysis and cross reference of information, allowing them to draw insights much quicker than ever before. The tool is based on large open ecosystems and libraries, including robust Web3D standards like glTF, established APIs like WebXR, and large community-driven libraries like THREE.js. The open-source ATON framework is designed to accelerate development and deployment of vertical Web3D/WebXR applications or tools like MuLaX, via a "plug and play" model. The framework is maintained, adopted in several national and international projects, and has a steadily growing community that is also gathered around design and development of vertical applications. We foresee large evolutions for MuLaX tool both inherited by underneath advancements of ATON, and through new projects, bringing new features as well as integration and accessibility improvements for targeted users.

.7 HSLU Migration Tool (AR Artwork Migration & Playback App)

Tool Name: HSLU Migration Tool – AR Artwork Migration & Playback App

Tool Owner: Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU)

Tool Type: Unity-based Migration & Reconstruction Tool (Legacy AR → Unity → Deployment Platform)

.7.1 Purpose

The HSLU Migration Tool enables the structured migration of legacy LAYAR-authored AR artworks into fully functional Unity scenes, preserving spatial relationships, object behavior, animations, and narrative structure. The tool supports the long-term preservation and re-publication of AR artworks originally created for deprecated platforms.

.7.2 Description

Developed at HSLU, the AR Artwork Migration & Playback App is a Unity-based pipeline that converts AR experiences originally authored in LAYAR into modular Unity scenes. The tool ingests JSON exports from LAYAR's MySQL database schema, including POI, Object, Transform, and Animation tables, and reconstructs object hierarchies, spatial layouts, transformations, and time-based behaviors.

To avoid reliance on deprecated GPS-based runtime systems, the tool computes the average of all POI coordinates to define a single Unity anchor point and converts all geospatial positions into relative local coordinates. This ensures preservation of the original spatial relationships while enabling deployment on contemporary AR platforms. Reconstructed scenes can be previewed in Unity and exported as optimized asset bundles via compatible deployment workflows (e.g. Hoverlay).

Required Inputs

LAYAR database exports (JSON):

POI (geospatial anchors)

Object (asset references, scale)

Transform (position, rotation, scale)

Animation (movement and time-based logic)

3D assets:

Wavefront .obj

.mtl material files

Associated texture files (.png / .jpg)

Optional:

Original database values for scale and orientation

Audio files referenced by URL (e.g. .mp3 / .wav)

Outputs

Reconstructed Unity scenes with:

Correct object placement and hierarchy

Preserved animations and temporal behavior

Local spatial anchoring

Export-ready asset bundles for AR deployment platforms

Dependencies / Environment

Unity 2022.3 LTS (URP project recommended)

Unity-based importer scripts developed at HSLU

Compatible Unity exporter workflow for deployment platform

Limitations

Does not rely on live GPS or AR Foundation geolocation

Uses averaged POI anchoring and relative coordinates

Some material and texture adjustments may require manual preparation

Not designed as an automated self-service tool; expert operation required

Status

Implemented and operational

Validated on multiple migrated AR artworks originally authored on the LAYAR platform

In addition to AI-based and image and signal processing tools, PERCEIVE includes partner-developed tools that support the migration, preservation, and re-publication of complex born-digital cultural heritage artefacts

created on deprecated platforms. These tools ensure long-term accessibility of legacy digital works by providing structured reconstruction and deployment workflows compatible with contemporary platforms.

.7.3 HSLU Migration Tool – AR Artwork Migration & Playback App

The HSLU Migration Tool, developed at the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU), is a Unity-based migration and reconstruction tool designed to convert legacy LAYAR-authored augmented reality artworks into fully functional Unity scenes. The tool enables the preservation and re-publication of AR experiences originally created for deprecated runtime environments by reconstructing their spatial layout, object hierarchy, transformations, animations, and narrative behaviour.

The tool ingests structured JSON exports from LAYAR's MySQL database schema, including POI, Object, Transform, and Animation tables. To preserve spatial relationships without relying on live GPS services, the migration process computes the average of all POI coordinates to establish a single anchor point in Unity and converts geospatial positions into relative local coordinates. This approach maintains the original spatial composition of the artwork while ensuring compatibility with modern AR platforms.

The reconstructed Unity scenes can be previewed and validated within the Unity environment and exported as optimised asset bundles using compatible deployment workflows, such as the Hoverlay Digital Sequence exporter. This allows migrated artworks to be deployed on mobile devices and AR glasses at original or newly defined locations.

Required inputs for the HSLU Migration Tool include Wavefront OBJ 3D assets with associated material and texture files, structured JSON exports from the original LAYAR database, and optional audio files referenced by URL. The tool is implemented and operational but requires expert operation and may involve manual preparation of materials and textures depending on the complexity of the original artwork.

.8 Light Damage Estimator (LDE)

.8.1 General Description and Scope

The Light Damage Estimator (LDE) is a web-based decision-support tool developed within the PERCEIVE project to predict and visualise colour changes in photosensitive materials exposed to light [1]. Its primary application lies in the preventive conservation of paintings and works on paper (PERCEIVE Scenario 2), although its framework can be extended to other photosensitive media such as textiles and photographs (Figure 5).

The LDE integrates experimental data that allows the simulation of cumulative colour changes over various time horizons and lighting conditions. The tool accepts digital image inputs and provides visual outputs designed to support conservators, heritage scientists, and museum professionals in assessing lighting-induced risks and defining long-term preservation strategies.

In concept and purpose, the LDE builds upon and extends previous efforts such as the Canadian Conservation Institute's (CCI) Online Light Damage Calculator [2], which has been adopted within the preventive conservation community. The CCI tool was designed to estimate colour change resulting from light exposure based on photometric intensity (illuminance) measurements and exposure duration.

While the CCI calculator relies on illuminance and cumulative light dose to provide general light damage estimates, the LDE introduces a spectrally resolved and image-based predictive framework. By incorporating measured spectral power distributions and experimentally determined degradation kinetics of photosensitive materials, the LDE allows users to explore the impact of different lighting solutions and scenarios on the colour of an artwork, based on the predictable change in material-specific areas of the object. This evolution represents a significant advancement in predictive capability, bridging experimental data and real-world lighting conditions for more precise, actionable decision-making in preventive conservation.

Main interface of the Light Damage Estimator (LDE) tool, allowing users to explore and visualise the predicted effects of light exposure on objects over time.

.8.2 User Requirements and Technical Approach

The development of the Light Damage Estimator (LDE) was guided by the specific needs of diverse user groups engaged in cultural heritage. Museum conservators and collection managers required an accessible means of quantifying object-specific risks from light exposure, moving beyond generic guidelines. Researchers and conservation scientists sought a framework that could integrate experimental data on pigment sensitivity into predictive simulations. Communication professionals and curators expressed the need for intuitive visualisations to facilitate dialogue with stakeholders and the public and ensure transparency in conservation decisions. Finally, the wider cultural industries and audiences benefit from a tool that translates complex scientific predictions into an interactive, understandable format.

From a technical perspective, the LDE is implemented as a modular web-based service, designed to be accessible across platforms without specialised software. It integrates spectral power distribution (SPD) data of light sources with colour change models that have been experimentally validated. The tool's architecture relies on open-source frameworks and is embedded within the microservice infrastructure of PERCEIVE platform, ensuring scalability and long-term maintainability.

The LDE emphasises interoperability with established standards. Colour predictions are expressed in the CIELAB 1976 colour space [3], allowing direct comparison with conservation guidelines and scientific literature. Image data management supports integration into museum imaging pipelines. In addition, the system is designed to interface with digital collection management systems and external repositories, thereby facilitating adherence to FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

.8.3 Key Features and Functionalities

The LDE offers a set of core capabilities designed to support preventive conservation workflows (Figure 6). The central module enables the dynamic visualisation of predicted colour changes in artworks under user-defined lighting scenarios. The user can define a lighting scenario by selecting a light source, specifying the light intensity in illuminance [lx] or in irradiance [$\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$] values, and defining the exposure time. For an exhibition, for example, the exposure time depends on the number of years, days per year, and hours per day defined by the user, as well as the total exposure dose (in either lx hours or $\mu\text{Wh}/\text{cm}^2$).

Interface for selecting pigments and exposure parameters (left), along with light sources (top right), to simulate and visualise colour changes under varying lighting conditions. Pigment masks extracted from the artwork (bottom right) provide the spatial information for computing the colour changes.

A simulation engine combines pigment-specific sensitivity data with the spectral distribution of the selected light source to estimate the expected colour differences caused by light exposure in the areas of the artwork where the specific pigments are mapped. It then generates visual predictions, which are displayed directly on digital images of the artwork.

The current release of the tool offers two different simulation methods:

1. The first method integrated into the tool provides a mechanistic explanation of pigment colour change caused by light-induced chemical reactions. It links light absorption to pigment degradation and correlates shifts in the CIELAB colour space with photochemical processes. The model incorporates the spectral power distribution of the light source, accounting for how different wavelengths influence degradation rates according to each pigment's absorbance profile. Long-term colour changes are expressed as a function of radiant exposure, enabling predictions to be made about fading or hue shifts under specific lighting conditions. However, it assumes that light is the primary driver of pigment degradation and does not include secondary environmental factors such as temperature or humidity. Derived coefficients describe the quantitative relationship between colour change and radiant exposure and are used to simulate future colour alterations. This photochemical method provides a predictive, physicochemical framework for assessing and managing light-induced deterioration in artworks.
2. The second method is based on a data-driven pigment photo-degradation model that operates in the hyperspectral domain to simulate light-induced colour changes in artworks. This method combines hyperspectral imaging of the painting with artificially aged pigment mock-ups that replicate the original material palette. Using spectral linear unmixing in the absorbance space ($-\log R$), the model identifies pigment abundance maps based on known spectral signatures and reconstructs the artwork by re-mixing them with aged spectra. This allows simulation of progressive pigment degradation under controlled light exposure. Applied to *The Scream* (ca. 1910), the model reproduced realistic pigment distributions consistent with analytical data and predicted darkening of vermilion regions with continued irradiation. Although some pigments lacked aging data, the model remains scalable—capable of integrating additional experimental datasets to refine future simulations of light-induced damage in paintings.

In terms of licensing and accessibility, the tool is made available as part of the PERCEIVE platform via a web interface. Currently, access is restricted to registered users within the consortium and associated institutions.

However, its modular design anticipates eventual release under an open-access or community license to support open access and broader adoption. An authentication service ensures the confidentiality and secure handling of institutional data, as well as integration with project repositories.

The LDE supports a variety of standard data types and formats, including digital images of artworks (standard PNG formats), spectral power distribution (SPD) data of light sources and pigment artificial ageing datasets in a CSV format. The outputs of each user session consist of interactive visualisations and downloadable analytical reports (CSV), which include the necessary metadata for the visualisations produced interactively. This ensures compatibility with existing documentation practices. The tool is designed for integration with other platforms, most notably the PERCEIVE Knowledge Repository and associated simulation services.

.8.4 Use Scenarios and User Profiles

The LDE has been designed to support diverse conservation and curatorial contexts by offering flexible workflows. A typical use case begins with the selection of a light-sensitive object for which a display plan or storage strategy is required. A preliminary study using an analytical imaging technique, such as macroXRF mapping or HSI imaging, is required to acquire pigment maps. These pigment maps are then aligned with the uploaded reference colour image of the object within the LDE application.

The user then selects a light source from the library of available predefined or known spectral power distributions. The user then selects from the list of identified pigments on the object those for which a light damage estimation is necessary due to their high sensitivity. The tool allows for the estimation of single and multiple pigments. A growing library of data produced by accelerated ageing experiments on mock-ups supports the tool. The tool simulates cumulative colour changes under user-defined exposure conditions and visualises the results interactively. It enables comparative evaluations based on visualisations corresponding to different lighting scenarios. These outputs and predicted images can be archived for conservation records or shared in exhibition planning discussions.

.8.5 Impact and Added Value

The LDE represents a significant advance in the field of preventive conservation by transforming laboratory-derived knowledge into a practical, accessible tool for everyday decision-making [4]. By embedding experimentally validated pigment sensitivity data into a user-friendly interface, the tool has bridged the gap between fundamental research and applied conservation practice. This enables museums and research institutions to move beyond generic light-exposure guidelines and adopt evidence-based, object-specific strategies for display and preservation.

The benefits of LDE are wide-reaching. In terms of knowledge creation, for example, it enables systematic documentation of predictable light-induced colour changes, generating new datasets that enrich both scientific research and conservation records alike. It also fosters collaboration between scientists, conservators, and curators, as the tool's visual simulations provide a basis for interdisciplinary dialogue. The tool offers researchers a structured environment in which to validate and extend predictive models and provides curators with a transparent means of communicating conservation risks to decision-makers and the public.

The LDE also improves accessibility and decision-making processes. Its visualisations enable non-specialists to grasp the potential consequences of light exposure, supporting transparent exhibition planning and risk communication. In terms of community building, the LDE is already fostering a user network within the PERCEIVE consortium, which includes leading museums and research institutions. Its modular web-based design will facilitate expansion to a broader community of practice in the future, enabling the sharing of workflows, case studies, and training initiatives.

Preliminary uptake indicators point to strong interest from PERCEIVE Scenario 2 institutions, where the tool has been piloted on paintings and works on paper. Although it is still under evaluation, the early adoption of

the LDE suggests its potential for integration into routine conservation workflows. In the long term, impact is expected to be reflected in measurable outcomes, such as the prevention of sensitive pigment alteration through informed lighting scenarios, the promotion of object-specific lighting strategies, and the incorporation of the LDE into professional training for conservators and museum staff.

.8.6 Sustainability and Future Developments

The sustainability of the Light Damage Estimator (LDE) is ensured through its integration within the PERCEIVE platform, which provides institutional hosting and ongoing technical support by a consortium of leading research organisations. Designed as a modular and extensible service, the tool can evolve in response to user feedback and advances in conservation science.

Planned updates and new features include the systematic expansion of the pigment sensitivity database through additional accelerated ageing studies, the incorporation of artificially aged pigment data, and the enhancement of visualisation options such as uncertainty mapping and side-by-side scenario comparisons. Future developments will also focus on the import of custom spectral profiles for light sources, the automated reporting of cumulative damage, and the export of simulation results for conservation documentation and analysis purposes.

The sustainability model is based on institutional hosting during and beyond the PERCEIVE project, with provisions for a community-driven development model as the tool matures. This will be supported by training workshops, user guides, and open-access documentation, encouraging widespread adoption. A growing user base will further strengthen sustainability by contributing case studies, validation data, and iterative feedback.

In terms of scalability and long-term maintenance, the LDE benefits from its API-based, web-service architecture, which facilitates interoperability with external repositories, digital collection management systems, and other heritage science tools. Compliance with widely adopted standards, including CIE colour metrics for predictive modelling and IIF protocols for image interoperability, ensures compatibility with emerging infrastructures in digital heritage.

Finally, the LDE is inherently customisable and extensible. Its modelling framework can accommodate new pigment sensitivity datasets, integrate multifactorial ageing parameters, and expand to additional visualisation modes. This flexibility guarantees that the tool will remain scientifically robust and practically relevant, positioning the LDE as a long-term reference resource for managing light-sensitive collections well beyond the lifetime of the PERCEIVE project.

.9 Conclusion

The tools in this chapter establish a robust technical framework for the preservation, study, and visualization of coloured collections through two primary categories: Machine Learning based and Image and Signal Processing based tools.

Key findings and contributions of the chapter include:

- **Diverse Technical Scope:** The project successfully delivers a suite of advanced tools, including StyleShade3D for 3D model stylization, the Degreening tool for restoring damaged autochromes, Text2Autochromes for generating synthetic training data, doLCE 2.0 for lenticular film reconstruction, MuLaX for multi-layered diagnostic data exploration, and the Migration tool for preserving legacy AR artworks.
- **Enhanced Conservation Workflows:** By leveraging AI Perceive tools significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of restoration and conservation efforts.

- **Accessibility and Collaboration:** The use of web-based APIs and microservice architectures ensures that these tools are accessible across different platforms, facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration between scientists, curators, and the public.
- **Sustainability and Future Growth:** The tools promote sustainable conservation by optimizing resource utilization and streamlining restoration processes. Future developments focus on increasing the autonomy of these tools to reduce reliance on technical experts, making advanced restoration technology more accessible to the broader heritage community.

In summary, D5.2.3 demonstrates that the PERCEIVE toolkit effectively bridges the gap between advanced research in AI/computer vision and the practical needs of cultural heritage preservation.

D5.2.4 Perceive Services

.1 Introduction

This section documents the PERCEIVE Platform Service Layer, the foundational infrastructure services that enable the platform’s cultural heritage digitisation, analysis, and preservation capabilities. These services form the operational backbone that supports scientific tools, manages user workflows, and ensures data integrity throughout the system lifecycle.

Service Portfolio Overview: The platform comprises eight specialised microservices, each addressing distinct functional requirements:

- **Authorisation Service:** OAuth2/OpenID Connect implementation using OpenIddict for standards-compliant authentication and token management
- **Identity Service:** User lifecycle management including registration, authentication, profile info, and privacy compliance
- **Orchestrator Service:** Asynchronous workflow coordination using message queue patterns to manage complex multi-step processing jobs
- **Data Service:** Storage abstraction layer providing unified access to Nextcloud-backed file repositories with WebDAV integration
- **Metadata Service:** Research data management through InvenioRDM integration ensuring FAIR principles compliance and long-term preservation
- **Email Service:** Transactional communication infrastructure supporting account verification and user notifications
- **Rating Tool Service:** Specialised service for managing image quality assessment workflows and collecting user feedback
- **Backend-for-Frontend (BFF):** API gateway aggregating downstream services into optimised client-facing endpoints

Key Architectural Characteristics:

- **Service Independence:** Each service maintains dedicated database schemas, independent deployment lifecycle, and autonomous scaling capabilities
- **Communication Heterogeneity:** Combines synchronous patterns (REST, gRPC) for request-response interactions with asynchronous messaging (RabbitMQ) for event-driven workflows
- **External Integration:** Seamless connectivity to enterprise-grade external systems (Nextcloud for storage, InvenioRDM for metadata) through abstraction layers protecting clients from provider-specific details
- **Shared Infrastructure:** Common observability stack (OpenTelemetry, Prometheus, Grafana), logging framework (Serilog), and a “service defaults” library ensuring operational consistency

Document Structure: D5.2.4 is organised into sections providing spherical description of the services. Section 2 presents detailed service component descriptions including functional responsibilities, technology stacks, key features, API endpoints, and requirements compliance for each service. Section 3 analyses inter-service communication patterns distinguishing synchronous REST/gRPC calls from asynchronous event-driven interactions. Section 4 examines deployment and runtime architecture covering containerisation strategies and observability integration. Section 5 concludes with readiness assessment and production deployment considerations.

Scope Clarification: D5.2.4 focuses exclusively on **infrastructure services** that provide core platform capabilities (authentication, storage, orchestration, metadata management). The **scientific processing tools** (e.g., Light Damage Estimator, De-Greening, Edge Detection algorithms) developed under PERCEIVE are outside this scope. These tools are presented in D5.2.3 and integrate with the platform through the Orchestrator Service's worker protocol, consuming orders from message queues and returning results to the Data and Metadata services. In a sense D5.2.4 is documenting the implementation of the Perceive API described in D5.2.2.

.2 Service Component Descriptions

This section provides comprehensive technical documentation for each microservice within the PERCEIVE platform, detailing their functional responsibilities, implementation technologies, key capabilities, and API contracts. Each service description follows a consistent structure:

1. **Function** defining the primary business responsibility and role within the overall architecture,
2. **Tech Stack** enumerating the frameworks, libraries, and infrastructure dependencies enabling service functionality,
3. **Key Features** highlighting distinctive capabilities and implementation patterns,
4. **Requirements Compliance** mapping service capabilities to specific functional requirements (FR) and Key Performance Indicators (KPI), and
5. **API Endpoints** documenting the primary interfaces exposed for client and inter-service communication.

The services are presented in logical dependency order, beginning with foundational authentication services (Authorisation, Identity) that secure access to all other components, proceeding through core workflow services (Orchestrator managing job coordination as shown in the Order Processing Figure below, Data providing storage abstraction, Metadata ensuring research data compliance), supporting services (Email, Rating Tool), and concluding with integration services (BFF , Service Defaults).

This organisation reflects the architectural principle that higher-level services depend on lower-level services but not vice versa, enabling independent development, testing, and deployment while maintaining system coherence.

.2.1 Authorization Service

- **Function:** Manages token issuance and access control policies.
- **Tech Stack:** .NET 8, **OpenIddict** (OAuth2/OIDC Server), Entity Framework Core.
- **Key Features:** Implements Client Credentials and Authorisation Code flows.
- *Validation:* Security Compliance (**PERC-API-KPI-0401**).

Endpoint	Description
GET/POST /connect/authorize	Initiate OAuth 2.0 authorization flow
POST /connect/token	Exchange authorization code for access/refresh tokens
POST /connect/logout	Terminate user session and revoke tokens
GET /connect/userinfo	Retrieve user profile information

.2.2 Identity Service

- **Function:** Handles user registration and profile management
- **Tech Stack:** .NET 8, ASP.NET Core Identity, PostgreSQL.
- **Key Features:** User registration, Email confirmation. Profile management, GDPR data export and deletion
- *Reqs:* Authentication flows (**PERC-API-FR-008**).
- *Validation:* Privacy Compliance (**PERC-API-KPI-0901**).

Endpoint	Description
POST /api/identity/register	Register a new user account
DELETE /api/identity/user	Delete current user account
GET/api/identity/user/export	Export current user's personal data

.2.3 Orchestrator Service

- **Function:** Manages complex, multi-step jobs and workflows.
- **Tech Stack:** .NET 8, **MassTransit** (RabbitMQ abstraction), PostgreSQL.
- **Logic:** Implements an Asynchronous Queue-based Workflow (see Figure 3).
- **Future Capability:** Architecture supports the **SAGA Pattern** for future complex distributed transactions.
- *Reqs:* High Concurrency (**PERC-API-NFR-0200**).

Endpoint	Description
POST /api/orders	Submit a new processing order
GET /api/orders/{orderId}	Retrieve details of a specific order
GET /api/orders/{orderId}/download	Download order results as ZIP
GET /api/workers	List all registered workers
GET /api/workers/{workerId}	Get details of a specific worker

Order Processing Workflow Sequence - This sequence diagram illustrates the asynchronous order processing workflow: (1) Client submits processing order to Orchestrator, (2) Orchestrator dispatches order event to RabbitMQ message queue, (3) External worker consumes order and executes processing, (4) Worker uploads result files to Data Service, (5) Worker publishes status updates via RabbitMQ, (6) Orchestrator receives status updates and stores final metadata in Metadata Service. This message-driven architecture decouples client requests from long-running processing operations.

.2.4 Data Service

- **Function:** Acts as an abstraction layer for file operations.
- Tech Stack: .NET 8, WebDAV Client, Npgsql.
- **Integration:** Connects via WebDAV/API to **Nextcloud** to ensure secure storage (see Figure 4).
- **Background Processing:** Uses **Hangfire** for recurring synchronisation jobs with Nextcloud.
- *Reqs:* File upload workflows (**PERC-API-FR-004**).
- *Security:* Encryption provided by Nextcloud (**PERC-API-NFR-1400**).
- *Validation:* Legal Compliance (**PERC-API-KPI-0501**).

Endpoint	Description
GET /api/resources/{id}	Retrieve resource metadata
GET /api/resources/{id}/download	Download resource file
POST /api/resources/upload	Upload a new resource

Data Ingestion and Storage flow

.2.5 Metadata Service

- **Function:** Handles CRUD operations for semantic metadata associated with digital assets.
- **Integration:** Maps PERCEIVE data models to **InvenioRDM** records to ensure FAIR principle compliance and long-term preservation.
- *Reqs:* JSON responses (PERC-API-FR-013), Monitoring (PERC-API-NFR-1000).

Endpoint	Description
POST /api/metadata/draft	Create a new draft record in InvenioRDM
POST /api/metadata/draft/{id}/files	Upload files to a draft record
POST /api/metadata/draft/{id}/publish	Publish a draft record
POST /api/metadata/complete-workflow	Create, upload, and publish in one step

.2.6 Email Service

- **Function:** Handles transactional emails (e.g., account confirmation, notifications).
- **Tech Stack:** .NET 8, **MailKit** (SMTP Client).
- **Integration:** Triggered asynchronously via RabbitMQ events or synchronously via gRPC for critical paths.

Endpoint	Description
GET /api/email-service/test	Test email sending (Development only)
gRPC ConfirmEmailService	Handle email confirmation requests

.2.7 Service Defaults (Shared Library)

- **Function:** Provides consistent setup for health checks, logging (Serilog), and OpenTelemetry telemetry across all services.

.2.8 Backend for Frontend (BFF)

- **Function:** Aggregates responses from Data, Metadata, and Orchestrator services to provide optimised payloads specifically for the Svelte frontend.
- **Tech Stack:** .NET 8, **YARP** (Yet Another Reverse Proxy).
- *Reqs:* API Gateway integration (**PERC-API-FR-011**).

.2.9 Servicebus

- **Function:** Asynchronous message broker (**RabbitMQ**) for decoupling services.
- **Reqs:** Horizontal Scaling backbone (**PERC-API-NFR-0300**).

.2.10 Rating Tool Service

- **Function:** Manages image quality assessment and rating workflows.
- **Tech Stack:** .NET 8, PostgreSQL.
- **Authentication:** Cookie-based session authentication.

Endpoint	Description
POST /api/rating-tool/session	Create a new rating session
POST /api/rating-tool/user-profile	Create an evaluator profile
GET /api/rating-tool/user-profile	Get current profile and session info
GET /api/rating-tool/image-set	Retrieve a set of images to rate
POST /api/rating-tool/rate-image	Submit a rating for an image

.3 Inter-Service Communication

In microservices architectures, service communication strategy fundamentally impacts system characteristics including latency, reliability, coupling, and operational complexity. The PERCEIVE platform employs heterogeneous communication patterns, selecting protocols based on operation semantics and performance requirements.

The communication architecture distinguishes between two primary patterns:

1. **Synchronous Communication** utilising REST-based HTTP calls for client-facing APIs requiring immediate response feedback, and gRPC with HTTP/2 for high-performance inter-service communication where low latency and type safety are prioritised (e.g., Authorisation Service querying Identity Service for user verification, Identity Service invoking Email Service for account confirmation), providing strong contracts through Protocol Buffer schemas and efficient binary serialisation.
2. **Asynchronous Communication** leveraging RabbitMQ message queues for event-driven interactions where temporal decoupling is beneficial (e.g., Orchestrator publishing order assignments to worker queues, Data Service emitting resource synchronisation events), enabling services to operate independently with resilience to temporary downstream unavailability, supporting publish-subscribe patterns for event broadcasting, and facilitating horizontal scaling through competing consumer patterns.

This hybrid approach optimises for different operational requirements: synchronous patterns minimise latency for interactive operations requiring immediate feedback, while asynchronous patterns maximise resilience and scalability for long-running workflows and background processing. The “Service Defaults” library standardises communication concerns including health checks, distributed tracing context propagation, and timeout policies across all communication patterns.

.4 Deployment & Runtime Architecture

Modern cloud-native applications require careful consideration of containerisation, orchestration, configuration management, and observability integration to achieve reliable production operations.

The deployment architecture addresses three fundamental concerns:

1. **Containerisation** packaging each service as immutable Docker containers with embedded dependencies, versioned images supporting rollback capabilities, multi-stage builds optimising image size and security posture, and consistent runtime environments eliminating “works on my machine” discrepancies, enabling deployment across heterogeneous infrastructure including on-premises Kubernetes clusters, cloud container services, and development workstations running Docker Compose.
2. **Orchestration** leveraging Kubernetes for production deployments with declarative service definitions (Deployments, StatefulSets), horizontal pod autoscaling based on CPU/memory metrics, service discovery through ClusterIP services and internal DNS, configuration management via ConfigMaps and Secrets, and persistent volume claims for stateful components (PostgreSQL databases, RabbitMQ storage), complemented by .NET Aspire for local development orchestration providing simplified service startup, automatic configuration injection, and integrated dashboard for monitoring during development cycles.
3. **Observability Integration** embedding OpenTelemetry agents within each container for automatic instrumentation, exposing Prometheus-compatible `/metrics` endpoints for scraping, forwarding structured logs to centralised aggregation systems, and implementing health check endpoints (`/health`, `/alive`) enabling Kubernetes liveness and readiness probes for automated failure detection and recovery.

The deployment model used in with PERCEIVE services supports progressive rollouts, blue-green deployments, and canary releases through Kubernetes deployment strategies, minimising downtime during updates while enabling rapid rollback if issues emerge. Infrastructure-as-code practices using Kustomize overlays manage environment-specific configurations (development, staging, production) without duplicating deployment manifests.

.5 Requirements Verification

This section provides a comprehensive view and status of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), Functional Requirements (FR), and Non-Functional Requirements (NFR) relevant to the PERCEIVE Services. Since most Services requirements and KPIs are directly or indirectly related to the performance of the PERCEIVE API, we provide references to the corresponding items of D5.2.2 in the “Implementation/Verification” column.

For the full table with descriptions (for both tools and services) the reader may refer to chapter 4 (D5.2.3) of the first version of this Deliverable (D5.2 v1).

FR/NFR ID	Name	Status	Implementation / Verification
PERC-T&S-FR-001	API Functionality	Implemented	Complete RESTful API via BFF gateway with endpoints for Users, Orders, and Resources. FastEndpoints framework provides strongly-typed, high-performance endpoint definitions. Swagger/OpenAPI documentation available at <code>/swagger</code> .
PERC-T&S-FR-009	User-Friendly Interface	Implemented	API designed following REST principles with consistent response envelopes (RFC 7807 for errors). Standardized JSON output format (PERC-API-FR-013). Interactive Swagger UI for API exploration.
PERC-T&S-FR-010	Reliable Analytics	Implemented	Comprehensive observability stack: OpenTelemetry instrumentation, Prometheus metrics collection, Grafana dashboards for real-time visualisation.

			Custom business metrics (Orders Created, Workers Registered, etc).
PERC-T&S-NFR-0100	High System Availability	Met	Health check endpoints (/health, /alive) on all services. Kubernetes deployment with liveness/readiness probes. Microservices architecture enables independent service recovery. Monitoring via Alertmanager for threshold-based notifications.
PERC-T&S-NFR-0200	Robust Data Security	Met	Multi-layered security: OAuth2/OpenID Connect via OpenIddict, RBAC authorization, Rate limiting at BFF level (YARP), TLS 1.2+ for transport, AES-256 encryption at rest via Nextcloud. Validated via PERC-API-KPI-0401.
PERC-T&S-NFR-0300	Scalability	Met	Microservices architecture supports horizontal scaling. Stateless service design allows load balancer distribution. RabbitMQ message queues prevent synchronous bottlenecks. Containerised deployment (Docker/Kubernetes) supports dynamic autoscaling. Validated +50% capacity (PERC-API-KPI-0301)
PERC-T&S-NFR-0400	Interoperability	Met	Standard protocols: REST/HTTP 1.1, gRPC/HTTP2 for inter-service, RabbitMQ for async messaging. External integrations: Nextcloud (WebDAV), InvenioRDM (REST API). OpenAPI/Swagger specifications for client code generation.
PERC-T&S-NFR-0500	Performance Efficiency	Met	Validated via load testing: See section 9 of D5.2.2.
PERC-T&S-NFR-0900	Flexible Image Library Support	Met	Worker architecture is agnostic to the implementation and libraries used by the tools. This is demonstrated by the plethora of tools implemented during the PERCEIVE project all using different libraries and stacks and running through the worker abstraction.
PERC-T&S-NFR-1300	Deep Learning Framework Support	Met	Similar to PERC-T&S-NFR-0900, Orchestrator Service implements asynchronous queue-based workflow via RabbitMQ. Workers (wrapping tools including DL models) consume orders, process data, and return results. Architecture supports any containerised processing tool.

KPI ID	Name	Target	Status	Implementation / Verification
PERC-T&S-KPI-0101	System Uptime	>99%	Passed	Health monitoring via `/health` and `/alive` endpoints. Kubernetes logs of the validation deployment over a period of several months support our high uptime claims.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0201	Security Incident Count	0	Passed	No security incidents reported during validation period.

PERC-T&S-KPI-0202	Encryption Compliance	AES-256	Passed	Data at rest encrypted via Nextcloud storage provider (AES-256). TLS 1.2+ for data in transit. Validated per PERC-API-KPI-1401.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0301	Load Capacity	>50 concurrent	Passed	Validated per PERC-API-KPI-0201.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0401	Integration Success Rate	>95%	Passed	External integrations operational: Nextcloud (WebDAV), InvenioRDM (REST). Worker protocol via RabbitMQ supports seamless tool integration. CORS configured for Portal cross-origin requests.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0402	API Compatibility Score	>8	Passed	OpenAPI 3.0 specifications for all services. Swagger UI for interactive exploration. Consistent REST design patterns. RFC 7807 error responses. Target aligned with PERC-API-KPI-0801 documentation quality
PERC-T&S-KPI-0501	Response Time Efficiency	<200ms	Passed	Validated via load testing: See section 9 of D5.2.2.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0502	Performance Under Load	<300ms	Passed	Validated via load testing: See section 9 of D5.2.2.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0601	User Interface Satisfaction	>8	Passed	Preliminary user survey that took place during the DH2025 expo showed high user satisfaction. The user studies are presented in D7.1 and D7.2.
PERC-T&S-KPI-0701	Analytical Accuracy	>95%	Passed	Accurate Services analytics are collected through OpenTelemetry by Prometheus and reported in Grafana as reported in section 7 of D5.2.2.

.6 Conclusions

In D5.2.4 we presented a comprehensive documentation of the PERCEIVE Platform Service Layer, demonstrating a mature, production-ready microservices infrastructure capable of supporting the complex requirements of cultural heritage digitisation, analysis, and preservation workflows.

Service Maturity: Each platform service implements well-defined business capabilities using industry-standard technologies (.NET 8, PostgreSQL, OpenIddict, gRPC) and proven architectural patterns (domain-driven design, event-driven architecture, repository pattern). The service portfolio provides complete coverage of infrastructure requirements.

Integration Readiness: The services successfully integrate with external enterprise systems (Nextcloud for storage, InvenioRDM for metadata management) through abstraction layers that insulate the platform from provider-specific implementation details. This approach ensures long-term flexibility to evolve storage and metadata infrastructure without requiring extensive system rework.

Operational Excellence: Comprehensive observability instrumentation with standardised metrics collection, structured logging, and distributed tracing provides the visibility necessary for production operations. Health check endpoints enable automated failure detection and recovery through Kubernetes orchestration. The

containerised deployment model supports modern DevOps practices including continuous integration, automated testing, and progressive rollout strategies.

Requirements Compliance: As presented in section 5 (Requirement Verification) of D5.2.4, all PERCEIVE Services-related functional and non-functional requirements are implemented or met. Additionally, all PERCEIVE Services KPIs defined in the T&S section of D5.2.3 are passed.

The Platform Services are ready to support the PERCEIVE ecosystem. They provide the necessary infrastructure for authentication, data management, and workflow orchestration, meeting the strict requirements for security, scalability, and performance.

Bibliography

- [1] Pescarin S, Aga B, Kiyomoto IYA, Barandoni C, Bonifazi F, Boracchi BG, et al. Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Coloured Collections through AI and Virtual Experiences. Digital Heritage [Internet]. 3350th ed. The Eurographics Association; 2025 [cited 2025 Sept 22]; <https://doi.org/10.2312/DH.20253350>
- [2] Canadian Conservation Institute. Light Damage Calculator [Internet]. Canada: Department of Canadian Heritage; 2019. <https://app.pch.gc.ca/application/cdl-ldc/description-about.app?lang=en>
- [3] Commission Internationale de l'Éclairage. Colorimetry. 3rd edition. Vienna: Commission Internationale de l'Éclairage; 2004.
- [4] Siozos P, Monico L, Romani A, Miliani C, Doherty B, Sandu ICA, et al. Light source classification and colour change modelling for understanding and predicting pigments discolouration. J Phys Photonics [Internet]. 2025 [cited 2025 Aug 20];7:035020. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7647/ade8c2>
- [5] V. Tanzu, "Spring | Home," VMware Tanzu, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://spring.io/>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [6] Microsoft, "ASP.NET Core," Microsoft, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/aspnet>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [7] Microsoft, "APIs with ASP.NET Core," Microsoft, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/aspnet/apis>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [8] TechEmpower, "Web Framework Benchmarks," TechEmpower, 19 07 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techempower.com/benchmarks/#section=data-r21&hw=ph&test=plaintext>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [9] Microsoft, "Real-time ASP.NET with SignalR," Microsoft, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/aspnet/signalr>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [10] Microsoft, "Microservices with .NET," Microsoft, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/apps/aspnet/microservices>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [11] Laravel, "The PHP Framework for Web Artisans," Laravel Holdings Inc., 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://laravel.com/>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].

- [12] Tiangolo, “FastAPI,” Tiangolo, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [13] StrongLoop, IBM, and other expressjs.com contributors, “Express | Fast, unopinionated, minimalist web framework for Node.js,” OpenJS Foundation, 1 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://expressjs.com/>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [14] pranay0911, “Spring Framework Architecture,” geeksforgeeks, 19 3 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.geeksforgeeks.org/spring-framework-architecture/>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [15] TechEmpower, “Web Framework Benchmarks Composite scores Round 22,” TechEmpower, 17 10 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.techempower.com/benchmarks/#hw=ph&test=composite§ion=data-r22>. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [16] u/le0bit115, “What Kind of Spring Boot Communities are out there?,” Reddit, 26 5 2021. [Online]. Available: https://www.reddit.com/r/java/comments/nlauoe/what_kind_of_spring_boot_communities_are_out_t_here/. [Accessed 1 7 2024].
- [17] a. S. m. e. al., “Common web application architectures,” Microsoft, 3 7 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/dotnet/architecture/modern-web-apps-azure/common-web-application-architectures>. [Accessed 2 7 2024].
- [18] R.-A. h. alexwolfmsft, “Deploying and scaling an ASP.NET Core app on Azure Container Apps,” Microsoft, 13 04 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/aspnet/core/host-and-deploy/scaling-aspnet-apps/scaling-aspnet-apps?view=aspnetcore-8.0&tabs=login-azure-cli>. [Accessed 2 7 2024].
- [19] j. e. a. IEvangelist, “.NET Aspire overview,” Microsoft, 23 05 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/dotnet/aspire/get-started/aspire-overview>. [Accessed 2 7 2024].
- [20] Microsoft, “Microsoft Learn. Spark possibility.,” Microsoft, 2 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/>. [Accessed 2 7 2024].
- [21] Microsoft, “Microsoft Community Leaders,” Microsoft, 2 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://mvp.microsoft.com/>. [Accessed 2 7 2024].
- [22] Microsoft, “.NET is Free,” Microsoft, 2 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/en-us/platform/free>. [Accessed 2 7 2024].
- [23] A. peter, “Fundamentals of Laravel Application Architecture,” Medium, 22 8 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://medium.com/@analiapeter53/fundamentals-of-laravel-application-architecture-838c0fd9e85>. [Accessed 3 7 2024].
- [24] K. Sangabriel, “PHP Microservice - Service Discovery,” Github, 1 1 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/ksangabriel/php-microservice-discovery>. [Accessed 3 7 2024].
- [25] Laravel.io, “The Laravel Community Portal,” Laravel.io, 3 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://laravel.io/>. [Accessed 3 7 2024].

- [26] P. Krampah, "FastAPI Project Setup With Scalability In Mind," Medium, 23 4 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://python.plainenglish.io/fastapi-project-setup-with-scalability-in-mind-3daef823ed83>. [Accessed 4 7 2024].
- [27] Meta Open Source, "React The library for web and native user interfaces," Meta, 23 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://react.dev/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [28] V. Bhagat, "10 Advantages of React for Building Interactive User Interfaces," [Online]. Available: <https://www.pixelcrayons.com/blog/dedicated-teams/advantages-of-react/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [29] Patrich, "Why React Became The Most Popular Frontend Framework In 2024," [Online]. Available: <https://slashdev.io/blog/why-react-became-the-most-popular-frontend-framework-in-2024>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [30] Carmatec, "The 20 Best JavaScript Libraries and Frameworks 2024," Carmatec, 7 11 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.carmatec.com/blog/the-20-best-javascript-libraries-and-frameworks/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [31] Svelte, "Svelte cybernetically enhanced web apps," [Online]. Available: <https://svelte.dev/>. [Accessed 23 7 2024].
- [32] Patrich, "The Ultimate Guide To Svelte Development In 2024," slashdev, [Online]. Available: <https://slashdev.io/blog/the-ultimate-guide-to-svelte-development-in-2024>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [33] techvify software, "Svelte vs React: A Full Comparison for 2024," techvify software, 25 3 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://techvify-software.com/svelte-vs-react/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [34] M. Jain, "Svelte vs React Framework 2024 – Pros, Cons, Use Cases," 19 3 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.konstantinfo.com/blog/svelte-vs-react/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [35] Microsoft, "Élaborez d'excellentes applications web avec Blazor," Microsoft, [Online]. Available: <https://dotnet.microsoft.com/fr-fr/apps/aspnet/web-apps/blazor>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [36] g. e. al, "ASP.NET Core Blazor," 2 9 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/aspnet/core/blazor/?view=aspnetcore-8.0>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [37] P. D. Tender, ".NET Blazor Overview and Upcoming .NET 8 Changes," sitepoint, 5 9 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sitepoint.com/net-blazor-overview/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [38] Unity, "Web Build Settings," Unity, [Online]. Available: <https://docs.unity3d.com/2023.2/Documentation/Manual/web-build-settings.html>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [39] Unity, "Build and distribute a WebGL application," Unity, [Online]. Available: <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/webgl-building-distribution.html>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [40] Unity, "WebGL," Unity, [Online]. Available: <https://docs.unity3d.com/Manual/webgl.html>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [41] Unreal, "Nous créons le moteur. À vous de créer.," Epic games, [Online]. Available: <https://www.unrealengine.com/fr>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].

- [42] Epic Games, "HTML5 Game Development," Epic Games, [Online]. Available: <https://docs.unrealengine.com/4.27/en-US/SharingAndReleasing/HTML5/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [43] L. Yen, "Cloud vs. On-Premises: Pros, Cons, and Use Cases," Datamation, 9 6 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.datamation.com/cloud/cloud-vs-on-premises-pros-cons-and-use-cases/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [44] A. Maricheva, "On-Premise vs. Cloud: The Debate Over IT Infrastructure," Softteco, 19 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://softteco.com/blog/on-premise-vs-cloud>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [45] K. Bhaduri, "On-Premise Infrastructure: Pros & Cons," Iron, 16 5 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://blog.iron.io/on-premise-infrastructure-pros-cons/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [46] F. Kompaniiets, "On-Premise to AWS Cloud Migration: A Step-by-Step Guide to Swiftly Migrating Enterprise-Level IT Infrastructure to the Cloud," Gartsolutions, 28 7 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://gartsolutions.com/on-premise-to-aws-cloud-migration>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [47] N. S., "On-Premises vs Cloud: Key Differences, Pros & Cons," CloudPanel, 19 9 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.cloudpanel.io/blog/on-premises-vs-cloud-computing/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [48] v2cloud, "On-Premises vs. Cloud: Pros, Cons & Key Differences," v2cloud, [Online]. Available: <https://v2cloud.com/blog/on-premise-vs-cloud>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [49] S. D. K. K. Marta Teneva, "On Premise vs. Cloud Migration: Costs, Benefits, and Considerations," b-eye, 7 5 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://b-eye.com/blog/on-premise-vs-cloud-comparison/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [50] J. Henretta, "On-Premises vs. Cloud Infrastructure," Skyward, 28 12 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://skywardit.com/blog/on-premises-vs-cloud-infrastructure/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [51] AscentOptics, "On-Premises Data Center vs Cloud: Making the Right Infrastructure Choice," AscentOptics, 22 2 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://ascentoptics.com/blog/on-premises-data-center-vs-cloud/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [52] Microsoft, "What is PaaS?," Microsoft, [Online]. Available: <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/resources/cloud-computing-dictionary/what-is-paas/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].
- [53] Platform.sh, "What is a PaaS? A Definitive Guide," Platform.sh, 12 9 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://platform.sh/blog/paas/>. [Accessed 22 7 2024].